

Challenge Solutions of the RibFrac Challenge

RibFrac Challenge Contributors

APPENDIX

A. Summary of Rib Fracture Detection Solutions

1) *Team lungseg2020 (DT1)*: Mask-RCNN [1] with FPN [2] and ResNet-50 [3] backbone is extended from 2D to 2.5D for rib fracture detection and segmentation. Since it is a 2.5D method, the 3D CT scans are split into slices, resulting in 44,000 positive samples and 11,000 negative samples in the training set. Positive and negative samples are randomly selected with a 1:1 ratio during training. Horizontal flip is employed for training time augmentation, and the model is pretrained on ImageNet. Considering the relevance of adjacent slices in 3D CT scans, multiple adjacent slices are used as input to capture more contextual information, while the network outputs the prediction result of the middle slice. Experiments on the relationship between model performance and the number of adjacent slices input are conducted, and it is found that 15 is the optimal choice. During inference, each slice in a CT scan is processed independently. Predictions below a certain threshold are disregarded. 2D predictions are merged into 3D based on connectivity, and the 3D prediction score is calculated as the average of the 2D prediction scores.

2) *Team DCC (DT2)*: A cascaded rib fracture detection pipeline is proposed, consisting of a 2D slice-level detection network and a 3D patch-level segmentation network. The 2D detection network uses the Mask-RCNN [1] model with ResNet [3] and HRNet [4] pretrained on ImageNet as the backbone. FPN [2] structure is added to enable multi-scale prediction. Random horizontal flip augmentation is applied to make the model learn invariant features. For the 3D segmentation network, U-Net [5] is employed to capture stereoscopic features using an iterative training strategy. The predicted masks of Mask-RCNN are combined with the ground truth to obtain the training samples for U-Net. The CT scans are cropped according to the center of each connected component before being fed into the network. Random rotation and flipping operations are performed for data augmentation. For model finetuning, predicted masks are integrated with ground truths to obtain new training samples.

3) *Team FakeDoctor (DT3)*: A two-stage rib fracture detection pipeline is proposed. It uses a ResUNet [6] structure for rib fracture segmentation, followed by a classification model to predict the segmentation results. The down-sampling stage of the nnUNet [7] model framework is replaced with ResUNet. Attention module and inflated module are applied to enlarge the subsampling receptive field. Combined binary cross-entropy loss and Dice loss are used as the loss function. In the post-processing stage of the segmentation model, prediction masks with smaller areas than the threshold are

eliminated, while the remaining prediction masks are expanded to be slightly larger than the fracture area. In the classification model stage, the predicted masks are cropped and normalized through an adaptive pooling layer before being fed into a VGG [8] network. The confidence level of each prediction mask is obtained after classification. Conventional data augmentation methods such as random rotation, translation, cutting, and blurring are employed.

4) *Team UClrvine (DT4)*: A segmentation-based model with model ensembling techniques is used for rib fracture detection. Two 3D U-Net [5] models are ensembled, one using binary cross-entropy loss and the other using Dice loss. The probability map is filtered with a threshold of 0.35, and each connected component is considered as an instance.

5) *Team MIDILab (DT5)*: An ensemble of 3D U-Nets [5] followed by morphological operations is applied for rib fracture detection. The model is based on a residual 3D U-Net [9], where all skip connections use element-wise addition instead of concatenation, and each module contains its own skip connection. The segmentation result is the voxel-wise mean of two residual 3D U-Nets, one trained on binary cross-entropy loss and the other on Dice loss [10], [11]. For post-processing, each prediction is upsampled to the dimension of the original CT scans. The prediction is binarized with a threshold, and missing voxels in connected fracture regions are filled in with a morphological binary closing operation. Small predicted fracture instances smaller than 512 mm^3 are removed to avoid over-prediction. In the final binary prediction, instance labels are assigned by identifying and numbering the connected components. The post-processing hyperparameters that maximize the validation FROC are determined by a grid search and used in all future runs.

6) *Team CCCCS (DT6)*: A 2D residual U-Net [5] is employed to segment rib fractures on 2D slices, followed by splicing the predictions into 3D as the post-processing operation. For data pre-processing, the ribs and their surrounding areas are extracted as input to address the problem of class label imbalance. The coronal slices are binarized with a threshold of 110 HU. A morphological dilation operation is applied to preserve soft tissues around the ribs. The binary images serve as the region-of-interest (ROI) masks, which are multiplied with the slices to obtain training data. Two slices of each annotation at the head and tail in the axial plane are disregarded to ensure that the rib fractures are clearly visible. The network architecture is a residual 2D U-Net, with hybrid dilated convolution [12] used to increase the receptive field. A two-stage training strategy is adopted to detect small rib fracture targets and reduce false-positive predictions simultaneously. Modified generalized Dice loss (GDL) [13]

is used to train a model with high recall, and then Tversky loss [14] is employed for false-positive reduction. In the post-processing stage, a morphological dilation operation on spliced 2D slices in the axial plane is performed to eliminate crevices in predictions across slices.

B. Summary of Rib Fracture Classification Solutions

1) *Team UCLrvine (CT1)*: 3D U-Net [5] with binary cross entropy is utilized for rib fracture segmentation. To limit the number of false positives, the probability map is filtered with a threshold of 0.95. For classification, the backbone of NoduleNet [15] is followed by three fully connected layers. A dropout layer is added between the last two fully connected layers to suppress overfitting. For data pre-processing, logarithm transformation is applied to the filtered and normalized CT scans, to balance out the effect of long tail data distribution. Each rib fracture in training and validation data is cropped into a 3D bounding cuboid with 4 extra pixels in each direction, with cuboid labeled -1 dropped. Random flipping, rotation, scaling and translation operations are conducted for training time data augmentation.

2) *Team DCC (CT2)*: 3D ResNet-50 [3] pretrained on Med3D [16] is used for rib fracture classification. Dilated convolutions [12] are applied in residual blocks to increase the receptive field while keeping the feature resolution. An auto-context mechanism [17] is adopted, where CT scans are integrated with masks generated by the segmentation model as the input of 3D ResNet-50 model. It demonstrated that the guidance of rib fracture mask could boost the classification performance. Random rotation and flipping operations are conducted to alleviate the over-fitting problem.

3) *Team DeepBlueAI (CT3)*: DeepMedic [18], a dual pathway structure, is employed as the baseline of rib fracture detection. A 3D CNN with parallel convolution pathways extracts highly accurate and soft segmentation features, followed with a fully connected 3D conditional random fields (CRF) to generate segmentation labels. The dual pathways share the same structure but have different input resolutions, so that both local and contextual information are incorporated. Shortcuts connections are utilized in the structure, similar as those in ResNet [3], to improve the training efficiency and boost performance. The segmentation features of the dual pathway 3D CNN are fed into fully connected layers, and then a 3D fully connected CRF with spatial regularization is used to generate smooth segmentation labels. Small connected components are removed for false-positive reduction.

4) *Team CCCC (CT4)*: 3D ResNet-18 [3] with weighted cross-entropy loss is applied for rib fracture classification. The classification method is based on the segmented regions in rib fracture detection task, which is described in the detection track. The 3D variant version of ResNet-18 is used as the backbone. Due to the extreme imbalance between classes, weighted cross-entropy loss is adopted, with the normalized reciprocal of the number of samples in each category in the training set as the weight.

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Detection Track lungseg2020 (DT1)

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Abstract. This report details our solution to the MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge [1] Detection Track. This challenge establishes a large-scale benchmark dataset to automatically detect and classify around 5,000 rib fractures from 660 computed tomography (CT) scans. We extended the multi-task learning framework Mask-RCNN from 2D to 2.5D and made several attempts to boost the performance from different aspects. Finally, we won second place with Public LB 0.8298 in the detection track.

1 Dataset

This challenge establishes a large-scale benchmark dataset [1] to automatically detect and classify around 5,000 rib fractures from 660 computed tomography (CT) slices, which consists of 420 training CTs (all with fractures), 80 validation CTs (20 without fractures) ,and 160 evaluation CTs. Each annotation consists of a pixel-level mask of rib fracture regions (for serving detection), as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. annotation example of rib fracture regions

We did some basic statistics on the lesions (based on the masks provided by the challenge), as shown in Table 1. z-length, y-length and x-length represents the length of the 3D lesion in z, y and x dimensions respectively. The length of each dimension is computed in pixels, and the data involved in the statistics are all raw data without being resized.

Table 1. lesion shape analysis

index	z-length	x-length	y-length
mean	17.2	18.4	21.1
std	11.83	8.4	10.8
max	117.0	70	99
min	3.0	1.0	1.0

2 Methods

In this section, we will describe our method used in this challenge in detail. We leverage Mask-RCNN [2] framework to do rib fracture detection and segmentation simultaneously. Since the 2D solution lacks contextual information, and the 3D solution takes a large amount of memory, we use the 2.5D solution to balance it, which is easy to implement with low memory usage and rich contextual information. In both training and inference stages, all the CT volume data are split into slices.

2.1 Mask-RCNN for Object Detection and Instance Segmentation

Mask R-CNN [2] extends Faster R-CNN [3] by adding a branch for predicting the lesion mask, in parallel with the existing branch for classification and bounding box regression (Fig. 2). This multi-task framework has a bunch of advantages. Firstly, multi-task learning is proven to be effective to benefit the relevant tasks. Secondly the mask branch only introduces a small computational overhead, enabling fast training speed and rapid experimentation. Last but not least such an end-to-end solution is more elegant than a segmentation model followed by a detection model, from implementation point of view.

2.2 Improvements

Multi-slices Input In natural image object detection tasks, the input data usually contains RGB channels. However, rib fracture object detection is a 3D object detection task in essence. The relation between adjacent slices should be considered because adjacent slices are often relevant in such specific tasks. Therefore, combining multiple adjacent slices should help obtain more contextual information than just inputting a single slice.

Fig. 2. Mask R-CNN framework for instance segmentation.

Multiple adjacent slices are used as the input of the network, and the output of the network is the prediction result of the middle slice. We did not predict multiple slices when inputting multiple slices at the same time, because in classical anchor-based object detection method, one anchor only predicts one object, and the object regions of adjacent slices are often very close, which makes it impossible to assign the best match anchor to all the objects.

The relationship between performance and number of adjacent slices input is studied, as shown in Table 2. Experiments show that the multi-slices input can boost performance by a significant margin compared with a single channel input. In our experiment, 15 is the best choice.

Table 2. the relationship between performance and number of adjacent slices input

Input channels	FROC(2D)
1	0.800
3	0.853
7	0.854
15	0.882
21	0.857

In this table, The FROC (2D) analysis is reported with sensitivities at various false positive (FP) levels of 2D predictions. We use the average of FP from 0.125 to 2 as our private evaluation strategy.

Sampling Strategy We split each volume into slices, the training set contains 44,000 positive samples with fractures and 110,000 negative samples without fractures. The information of the negative samples is shown to be helpful in our

experiment. During train sampling, we randomly select positive and negative samples by 1:1, which can help improve the FROC (2D) by 1.8 points compared with positive only sampling strategy.

Pre-trained Model When training the model on small data set, initializing with a pre-trained model of a large-scale data set and fine-tuning the parameters on private data set can accelerate convergence and improve performance [4]. ImageNet [5] pre-trained model is adopted in our experiment. Due to the number of input channels is different from pre-trained model, we initialize the first convolution layer following [6]. Moreover, the parameters of the first stage in resnet [7] are frozen in training stage, which can help improve performance by 0.4 points in our experiment.

Data Augmentation We only use the horizontal flip for data augmentation.

Bone Windows In CT images, in order to visualize the details in the tissue of interest, the reader can adjust the contrast and brightness of the image according to the needs of diagnosis. In our experiment, we selected several different windows to clip the inputting pixel values: (1): min=-100, max=1300; (2): min=-600, max=1500; (3): min=-400, max=1000. Unexpectedly, experiments show that different window settings have no significant effect on the result.

Anchor Selection We observed that the rib fracture lesions are relatively smaller compared with other object detection tasks. In our experiment, we use smaller anchors (sizes:16, 32, 64, 128, 256. aspect ratios:0.5, 1.0, 2.0) per position for each FPN [8] level.

2.3 Implementation Details

Our work is implemented with PyTorch 1.6. We use Mask-Rcnn with FPN and Resnet-50 backbone. The model is trained on the official training set of MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge and evaluated online.

Training We set the initial weight of the base extractor by the weights of the ImageNet classification pre-trained model. We use SGD with momentum 0.9 and weight decay 0.0001. The initial learning rate is set to 0.005. The batch size is set to 4 and the max iteration is 110,000. We only use single scale training.

Testing We evaluate the last checkpoint after training. No test time augmentation is used. Each slice in a CT series is inferred, and the input image is a series of adjacent slices centered on the current slice as in training. NMS operation (with IoU threshold sets to 0.01) is used in 2D predictions. After inference, the isolated 2D image prediction results are merged into 3D predictions. Here,

we set a single threshold and remove the predictions below the threshold. Then merge 2D objects into 3D objects based on connectivity, and the score of the 3D objects is the average of the 2D objects prediction scores.

2.4 Result

The final model uses all above-mentioned optimal settings, such as multiple adjacent slices input, model fine-tuning, horizontal flip for data augmentation, resize long side of input image to 800. On the official validation set, FROC (2D) is 0.907, and the online evaluation result on the test set is 0.8298.

3 Conclusion

In this paper, we described the details of our solution to the MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge Detection Track. We won 2nd place with FROC score 0.8298. Unfortunately, when we started to work on this challenge, there were only a few days left for us, and many potential ideas had not been tried. For instance, a well-designed post-processing strategy, more powerful backbones, different data augmentation strategies, 3D based solution, test time augmentation, model ensemble, etc. In future work, we plan to explore the effects of above-mentioned tricks together with new techniques.

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Detection Track DCC (DT2) & Classification Track DCC (CT2)

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Abstract. Diagnosis of rib fractures serves as an important and common task in clinical practice. An accurate and automatic method for rib fracture detection is highly demanded to assist radiologists and to improve the efficiency of clinical diagnosis. Recently, many deep-learning based models have been proposed for object detection and segmentation. However, most of those models were based on the 2D convolutions which can not leverage the spatial information along the z dimension thus limited the performance on the detection tasks of rib fractures. In this work, we proposed a cascaded detection algorithm based on deep neural networks for automated rib fracture detection and segmentation, which consists of a 2D detection network to detect and segment the rib fractures on the 2D slice-level; and a 3D segmentation network to segment the rib fractures on the 3D patch-level. Furthermore, we adopted a 3D ResNet with dilated convolutions to enhance the model with large receptive fields for rib fractures classification. We evaluated the proposed method on the official testing set of RibFrac 2020 challenge and achieved the best balance performance on both detection and classification track, which ranked 3rd and 2nd respectively.

1 Introduction

Rib fractures are the most common complication in chest trauma, which is mainly caused by external violent impact on the patients chest[6]. The location, alignment, and quantity of rib fractures seriously affect the clinical treatment of patients. In clinical diagnosis, radiologists need to investigate the rib fractures from hundreds of CT images, which is time-consuming and prove to misdiagnosis. Therefore, automatic rib fracture detection methods are highly demanded to reduce the missed diagnosis rate and improve the efficiency of clinical diagnosis. However, to our best knowledge, few prior studies with automatic machine learning techniques were investigated on this labor-intensive task. In this work, we proposed a cascaded detection method to detect the rib fractures among the chest CT scans and a 3D classification model to distinguish the rib fractures into four categories including buckle, displaced, nondisplaced, and segmental rib fractures.

Fig. 1. Schematic view of our proposed framework.

2 Methodology

Fig. 1 is the schematic view of our proposed framework. We first adopted the 2D Mask R-CNN[4] model to detect and segment the rib fracture on the 2D slice-level, then a 3D UNet[8] model were used to segment the rib fracture on the 3D patch-level and suppress the false positives. The final rib fracture mask was the ensemble result of masks from the 2D Mask R-CNN[4] and 3D UNet model and the confidence of each rib fracture was the average value of their top k probabilities. For the rib fracture classification task, we developed a 3D dilated ResNet model which took the rib fracture proposals with the corresponding probability maps from the segmentation models as inputs.

2.1 2D Detection and Segmentation

Recently, the algorithms of object detection based on deep-learning can be mainly grouped into two genres: 1) two-stage detection and 2) one-stage detection. The two-stage methods first used a region proposal network(RPN)[7] to generate potential bounding boxes in an image and then a classifier was used to get the class probabilities of these proposed boxes, while the one-stage methods taking object detection as a regression problem and obtaining the bounding box coordinates and class probabilities from the image pixels directly. In this study, we used the Mask R-CNN[4] model, a two-stage detection network, to detect and

segment the rib fractures of the chest CT scans for its superior accuracy on both the detection and segmentation tasks.

Specifically, we implemented two state-of-the-art 2D networks including ResNet[3], and HRNet[9] as the backbone of the Mask R-CNN model, which were pre-trained on the ImageNet competition dataset[1]. Besides, the FPN (Feature Pyramid Network)[5] structure was added into the basic Mask R-CNN detector, which consists of top-down architecture with lateral connections to fuse multi-scale features and significantly improving the performance of the detector.

2.2 3D Segmentation

2D networks with deep convolutions ignore the spatial information along the z dimension therefore lose the ability to capture the 3D features of data. In this work, we used a 3D deep neural network named UNet[8], which consists of a series of 3D convolutions to efficiently capture stereoscopic features and a decoder to recover the spatial information, to improve the accuracy of rib fracture segmentation. Besides, an iterative training strategy was proposed to selectively search informative samples and improve training efficacy.

Specifically, we first integrated the predicted mask of the Mask R-CNN[4] model with the ground truth to get the samples to train the UNet model. The training samples were cropped from the original CT images according to the center of gravity coordinates of each connected component. Then we use the model to predict the training data by sliding window and add the predicted mask with the ground truth to get the new training samples to finetune the model.

2.3 3D Classification

As aforementioned, the 3D convolutions can efficiently exploit the rich information contained in the 3D volume data and get better performance. In this study, we adopted the 3D ResNet50[3] pre-trained in[2] to speed up training and improve the stability of the model. Besides, we utilized dilated convolutions in residual blocks which can increase the receptive field and keep the feature resolution. Inspired by the auto-context mechanism, we integrated the original CT image with the output of the segmentation model as the input of our 3D ResNet[3] model, which can alleviate the optimization burden and improve training efficiency.

Specifically, dilated convolutions with rates of 1, 1, 1, 2, 4 were adopted in residual blocks (L1, L2, L3, L4, L5) and the strides are 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, respectively. The input volume with a size of $2*96*96*24$ was generated by the concatenation of two cropped patches from the original CT image and the output of the segmentation model in the same position.

3 Experimental Results

Dataset and preprocessing: We used solely the official data provided by the RibFrac competition to train and validate the model. The RibFrac datasets include about 5000 rib fractures from 660 cases of CT data, of which 420 cases (all with fractures) and 80 cases (20 without fractures) are used as the training set and validation set, and the remaining 160 cases are testing set. We truncated the image intensity values of all scans to the range of $[-361, 797]$ to ignore irrelevant image details and the min-max normalization method was used to normalize the data to $[0,1]$. For the Mask R-CNN[4] model, we first conducted random horizontal flip augmentation to make models learn invariant features to geometric perturbations, then the image size was finally scaled to $1024*1024$. For the 3D UNet[8] model and the 3D ResNet[3] model, we adopted random rotation(90, 180, 270) and flipping to alleviate the over-fitting problem.

Implementation details: All models were implemented with the *PyTorch* using NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN Xp GPUs. For the Mask R-CNN[4] model, we set the multi-aspect ratios of anchors as (1:2,1:1,2:1) at each level as in [5]. Formally, an anchor was considered as a positive label if it has an IoU over 0.5 with any ground-truth box or the highest IoU for a given ground-truth box, and the anchor which has IoU lower than 0.3 for all ground-truth boxes was defined as a negative label. Adam optimizer with learning rate initialized as 0.01 was used to update the weight of the model. For the 3d UNet[8] model, we adopted an Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001 to update the parameter of the network and the batch size was set to 2 for each GPU. For the 3D ResNet[3] model, we used pre-trained MedicalNet[2] as the initial weights and the Adam optimizer was applied with a learning rate of 0.0001 to optimize our model.

Evaluations Metrics: The FROC (Free-Response Receiver Operating Characteristic) analysis which reports with sensitivities at different false positive (FP) rates was used in this challenge to evaluate the detection performance of rib fracture. Specifically, the mean sensitivity of the five false positive rates (0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 8) was selected as the overview challenge metric for the detection task and a predicted rib fracture was regarded as a true positive only if it has an IoU over 0.2 between any rib fracture annotation. For classification task, the challenge used the Macro-average F1 score by the 4 categories including buckle, displaced, nondisplaced, and segmental as the evaluation metric.

Quantitative and Qualitative Analysis: Table.1 lists the detection performance of different methods. It is observed that independently using the Mask R-CNN[4] model or the UNet[8] model to detect rib fractures cannot achieve a satisfactory performance. The 2D Mask R-CNN[4] models got high sensitivities with high false-positive rates but the sensitivity at the false positive rate of 0.5 is 0, while the 3D UNet[8] model got a more balanced sensitivity at different

false positives but the highest sensitivity is lower than 0.8 (0.775). However, the mean sensitivity of the five false-positive rates (0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 8) was significantly improved with the cascaded version of the Mask R-CNN[4] model and UNet[8] model, which demonstrates that the proposed cascaded algorithm incorporating the 2D detection network and the 3D segmentation network can be complementary with each other and bring a boost in detection performance. The performance of the classification task is shown in Table.2. It occurred an improvement when the auto-context mechanism was adopted, which proved that the guidance of the rib fracture mask from the segmentation model can boost the classification performance of rib fracture. The proposed method was evaluated on the official 160 testing set of RibFrac2020 and the performance was shown in Table.3. The best balance performance on both detection and classification of rib fracture was taken by our team, which respectively achieved the third and second place for the tasks of rib fracture detection and classification.

Table 1. Detection performance of the proposed algorithm on validation dataset

Method	Backbone	Sensitivity					average
		FP=0.5	FP=1	FP=2	FP=4	FP=8	
Mask R-CNN [4]	ResNet50[3]	0.000	0.495	0.594	0.687	0.751	0.507
	ResNet101 [3]	0.000	0.779	0.854	0.890	0.906	0.686
	HRNet32 [9]	0.000	0.729	0.741	0.832	0.887	0.638
UNet [8]	-	0.538	0.636	0.693	0.735	0.775	0.675
Cascaded Strategy	ResNet50 [3]	0.625	0.698	0.735	0.771	0.795	0.725
	ResNet101 [3]	0.687	0.772	0.833	0.883	0.899	0.815
	HRNet32 [9]	0.634	0.757	0.826	0.864	0.897	0.796
ensemble	-	0.694	0.789	0.845	0.895	0.903	0.825

Table 2. Classification performance of the proposed method on validation dataset

Backbone	Method	F1 score				average
		buckle	displaced	nondisplaced	segmental	
3D Dilated ResNet	w/o auto-context	0.103	0.296	0.252	0.321	0.243
	w/ auto-context	0.098	0.330	0.230	0.340	0.249
ensemble	-	0.099	0.333	0.247	0.333	0.253

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed a deep cascaded learning method for the detection and classification of rib fractures from the chest CT scans. Experimental results in the RibFrac2020 challenge demonstrated the efficacy of the proposed method.

Table 3. Performance of official leader board

Task	Team	Performance
Detection	Yizhun	0.8502
	lungseg2020	0.8298
	ours	0.8114
	FakeDoctor	0.7630
	UCIrvine	0.7429
Classification	UCIrvine	0.3038
	ours	0.2560
	DeepBlueAI	0.2332
	c	0.2311
	CCCCS	0.2257

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Detection Track FakeDoctor (DT3)

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● Introduction

Diagnosis of rib fractures serves as an important and common task in clinical practice, forensics and several business scenarios. However, few prior studies investigate automatic machine learning techniques on this labor-intensive task. For this Ribfrac challenge, artificial intelligence is used to detect and classify rib fractures, and segmentation algorithm is used as the basis for detection of rib fracture area. Then, the confidence level is calculated by classifying the segmentation results. After validation, the performance of our method reaches a good level under the given metric.

● Detection

● Model Architecture

The detection task needs to implement instance segmentation. the evaluation is based on FROC analysis for detection. Considering the complexity of instance segmentation task, we adopt a two-stage model as the task architecture. Firstly, a ResUnet structure is used to segment the rib fracture region, and then a classification model of rib fracture label is established to predict the segmentation results in the first stage. For ResUnet, we use the model framework of nnUnet. In the down sampling stage of Unet, we replace it with ResUnet and introduce the residual network structure of ResUnet.

For the classification network, the model architecture of vgg19 is used.

For the loss function of the model, considering that the rib fracture area is a small target, the combined loss of CE + dice is used as the loss function.

● Data

This challenge establishes a large-scale benchmark dataset to automatically detect and classify around 5,000 rib fractures from 660 computed tomography (CT) scans, which consists of 420 training CTs (all with fractures), 80 validation CTs (20 without fractures) and 160 evaluation CTs.

These data are 3D data. Their x and Y axes are 512x512 pixels, and the number of layers on Z axis is different. However, the layer thickness of different CT is different. There are three kinds of layer thickness, which are 1 mm, 1.25 mm and 0.625 mm. For different layer thickness, the data should be interpolated into a uniform size. Considering the distribution of different layer thickness of data, the uniform interpolation should be 1 mm. Because of the label value in the training data, the nearest neighbor interpolation method is used to interpolate the values of different layer thickness into 1 mm.

For CT data, different window width and window level should be adjusted according to different organs and targets. For ribs, the window width of 1400 and 350 is appropriate. To adjust the window width and window level, it is necessary to convert the instance segmentation data into the semantic segmentation data, which requires the unification of the data in the label, the label data into 1, the background into 0.

After the preliminary processing of the data, we use the data preprocessing method provided by nnUnet. First, we crop the whole data (only in the non-zero region, so as to reduce the calculation consumption),

and then try to use the high-resolution processing of nnUnet's own data to further improve the data clarity. In addition, the data will be further augmented when the model is loaded. Data augmentation includes data rotation, translation, cutting, fuzzy and other conventional data augmentation methods.

- Train and Validation

We conduct all our experiments on one RTX 2080ti GPU using the Pytorch 1.3 deep learning platform. The training process ends at 700 epoches, which takes approximately 108 hours.

For the verification model, the nnunet framework can directly verify the model. It does not directly use the FROC algorithm specified in the competition to verify the model because the core of the FROC algorithm code is to calculate the IOU between the predicted mask and the ground truth to count the hit.

- Model Features

In the framework of the model, the original UNet is rewritten to 3D-Unet, and then the down sampling is replaced by ResNet. The residual network module is added in the subsampling to increase the depth of the down sampling. In addition, the attention module and inflated module are added to make the subsampling receptive field larger and pay more attention to the fracture edge information. There is nothing special about upsampling, which is the original structure of UNet.

At first, during the validation, it was found that the model results were particularly poor. According to the comparison between the prediction results and the ground truth, it is found that there are many very small pixel blocks in the prediction results. These small pixel blocks image the detection effect, but we can not rule out that the prediction effect of our model is not good, or it may be that the effect of our model is excellent, but there is a problem with the labeling of the organizer's data itself. In addition, we found that most of the ground truth was slightly larger than the actual fracture area. In order to achieve good results, we first calculate the voxel size of ground truth and find the smallest voxel value. In the post-processing of the model, the first step is to set the threshold, eliminate the prediction mask whose voxel value is less than the threshold value, and then expand the prediction mask of each voxel level to a certain extent, so that the prediction mask is slightly larger than the fracture area. In addition, we found that the predicted mask has multiple prediction positions that are not correct. It's segmented in the scapula or spinal region. For these, we are in the second stage of the classification model to remove.

In the stage of classification model, we first segment the predicted mask according to its size, then unify the size through an adaptive pooling layer, and then use a Vgg network to classify the results. For the previously mentioned abnormalities of scapula or spine, we can screen out and eliminate them in this step. According to the classification results, the confidence level of each prediction mask is obtained.

Detection Track UCIrvine (DT4) & Classification Track UCIrvine (CT1)

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Abstract. Diagnosis of rib fractures is an essential task in clinical practice, forensics and several business scenarios [1]. In this solution, we exploit different 3D object detection, segmentation and classification models that we developed in the RibFrac 2020 Challenge [1]. This solution achieved a top 5 average FROC in the detection (instance segmentation) track and top 1 macro F1 score in the classification track.

Keywords: rib fracture detection, segmentation and classification · deep convolutional neural network

1 Introduction

Rib fractures are the most commonly observed skeletal injury following thoracic blunt trauma, and occur in around 50% of these individuals. [3] However, there are few research investigating automatic machine learning algorithms on detecting and classifying rib fractures. [1] Automatic detection and classification can be a promising tool for this labor-intensive task.

2 Dataset

This dataset has 660 3D computed tomography (CT) images in total, including 420 in training set, 80 in validation set and 160 in test set. Each image in training set at least contains one rib fracture, while validation and test images may or may not contains one. Each rib fracture is human-labeled and represented as a 3D mask with a fracture class. The width and height of all the CT images are 512 by 512 while the depth may vary from image to image. Each voxel contains a Hounsfield Units (HU) value, whose min value is -1024.

3 Tasks and Evaluation Metrics

There are two tasks in this challenge, detection and classification, while classification algorithms need to be developed based on the detection algorithm predictions.

3.1 Detection

Rib fractures are labeled as 3D masks in this dataset. Therefore, the detection task is actually required to be implemented in an instance segmentation fashion. Free-Response Receiver Operating Characteristic (FROC) analysis is adopted as an evaluation approach balancing both sensitivity and false positives. The FROC analysis is reported at different false positive (FP) levels: 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8. For each ground truth rib fracture, if the prediction mask has a IoU larger than 0.2, it's considered as a hit.

3.2 Classification

Each rib fracture in this dataset has a class label. Segmented instances from the detection algorithm need to be assigned with a class label. The macro F1 score is taken as the evaluation metrics. Note that the macro F1 score is highly affected by false positives, thus false positive reduction in task 1 is essential.

4 Method

We explored semantic segmentation models and object detection models for task 1 during the challenge. Object detection models [5][9], have high sensitivities, yet with high false positive rate. Semantic segmentation models, e.g. the U-Net [6] family, don't have such high sensitivity upper bound due to the unbalanced distribution of rib fracture regions and non rib fracture regions, however, achieve higher sensitivity with a relatively low false positive rate.

As the macro F1 score is highly affected by false positives and we intend to achieve a higher macro F1 score in the classification task, we need to balance the sensitivity upper bound and the number of false positives. Therefore, after the trade off, our solution is based on segmentation models.

4.1 Detection

Our detection model is a segmentation based model. In our submission with the highest average recall, we ensemble a 3D U-Net [6] model with binary cross entropy loss and a 3D U-Net model with Dice loss. We pick 0.35 as a threshold to filter the final probability map and assign each connected component as an instance (rib fracture). This ensemble model ends up with a 0.6425 average recall on validation set and a 0.7429 average recall on test set. Note that there is a 10% average recall gap between validation set and test set, which is possibly caused by:

- the proportion of healthy cases in test set is larger than the one in validation set.
- the data distribution of test set is more consistent with the one in training set.

4.2 Classification

In our submission with the highest macro F1 score, we only use the output of 3D U-Net model with binary cross entropy loss with no model ensemble. We pick 0.95 as threshold to filter the final probability map because in this task there's an urgent demand of limiting the number of false positives. Our model ends up with a 0.2765 macro F1 score on validation set and a 0.3038 macro F1 score on test set. This result is limited by the detection model and may be boosted significantly with a higher sensitivity detection model.

Model Structure We apply the backbone of NoduleNet [9] as our feature extractor and output a $128 \times 16 \times 16 \times 16$ feature map. Three fully connected layers with 512, 128 and 4 output channels are then applied to the feature map. To suppress overfitting, we also add a dropout layer between the 2nd and 3rd fully connected layer.

Data Preprocessing For each CT image, we firstly filter HU values from 100 to 2048 to get the bone region and normal them between 0 to 1. Then we apply logarithm transformation, i.e. $f(x) = \log(1 + x)$, in order to balance out the affect of long tail data distribution. For each rib fracture in training and validation data, we crop a 3D bounding cuboid with 4 extra pixel in each direction. Cuboids labelled -1 (the class Ignore) are dropped in this process. We resize these cuboids to $64 \times 64 \times 64$ cubes. During inference, we take the 3D mask of each instance from the detection model and apply the same procedure above to these masks to get the preprocessed cubes.

Data Augmentation During training of our model, we apply flip, rotation, scaling and translation as our data augmentation method. Note that according to our experiment, rotate is essential to reduce overfitting in this task.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Detection Based Models

During the challenge, we also explored several detection based models for the detection task, e.g. NoduleNet [9] and Faster RCNN [5]. Detection based models may achieve higher sensitivity upper bounds but it's hard to control the number of false positives. Due to the evaluation metrics in this challenge, we adopt the segmentation based model for detection. Note that rib fractures are mostly

elongated objects in this dataset. It might not be suitable to directly apply 3D bounding boxes to them. It might be an open problem to effectively suppress the false positives.

5.2 Segmentation Based Models

The outputs of segmentation models are probability maps. We get masks for each instance by thresholding the probability map. In this challenge, there's no overlap between rib fractures, so segmentation models seem quite suitable. However, due to the class imbalance problem, it's easier for the model to predict a voxel as background rather than a rib fracture, which may lead to a low sensitivity upper bound for segmentation based models. To tackle this problem, we also applied different loss functions, e.g. Generalized Dice Loss [8], Focal Loss [4], Tversky Loss [7] and Lovasz Softmax [2], but we didn't see any significant performance improvement. It might be an open problem to mining more true positive instances.

5.3 Classification Models

Due to limited time, we only tried the backbone of NoduleNet [9] as our feature extractor. Compared to the state of the art classification models, our model don't have surprisingly large number of parameters but we still see a large defect of overfitting. We applied dropout layers, global max pooling layers and also tried different data augmentation methods. The severe overfitting was improved significantly but still exists. It might be an open problem to reduce overfitting properly.

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Detection Track MIDILab (DT5)

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Abstract. While rib fracture diagnosis is a common, labor-intensive clinical task, there have been few attempts to automatically segment and detect rib fractures with deep learning methods. This represents a difficult multi-instance detection task due to its three-dimensional (3D) nature and severe class imbalance. We show that a simple ensemble of 3D U-Nets can detect rib fractures in computed tomography (CT) scans. Our best-performing model consisted of a voxel-wise average of two residual 3D U-Nets, one trained on a standard cross-entropy loss and the other on a “soft” intersection-over-union (IOU) loss. After averaging predictions, we apply a series of morphological operations to label each segmented region. When evaluated on the online test set of the MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge, our semantic segmentation ensemble approach achieved a detection FROC of 0.6665.

Keywords: rib fracture detection · U-Net · 3D segmentation

1 Introduction

Multi-instance detection is a common task in radiology. Deep learning methods to accomplish this task commonly are based on object detectors with outputs including the coordinates of candidate bounding boxes and probabilities of class membership. Alternatively, this can be treated as a segmentation task. We applied an ensemble of 3D U-Nets to segment fracture-present locations and then applied morphological operations to assign instance labels to each location. This solution was developed in response to the MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge.

2 Methods

Data Pre-Processing: Each of the 500 raw CT volumes had dimensions $512 \times 512 \times Z$, where Z is the number of cross-sectional slices provided in a particular series. After reading in each CT we thresholded voxel values to have a minimum of -1000 Hounsfield units (HU). We then downsampled the whole CT volume to dimensions $192 \times 192 \times 192$ with bi-linear interpolation in order to train on whole CT images rather than smaller subvolumes that only provide local information; Finally, we removed the patient table from each image with a custom

function and then normalized each image (\mathbf{X}) with the following transformation: $\mathbf{X} := \frac{\mathbf{X} - \min(\mathbf{X})}{2000 - \min(\mathbf{X})}$, where 2000 HU serves as an approximate “global” maximum value by which to normalize all images.

Loss Functions and Class Weights: One downside of electing to train on whole CTs is that fracture voxels, if present at all, make up a very small proportion of a CT image, resulting in severe class imbalance; for instance, after pre-processing the training data, we found that each 192x192x192 image had a mean fracture prevalence of 0.04%. A common approach to such imbalance would be to weight the foreground class by the inverse of its frequency in the training set in the loss computation; however, in this particular case, that would mean giving over 2000-fold weight to the fracture class, which we found to actually hinder optimization and ultimately performance on the validation and test sets.

Instead, we used smaller foreground weights (e.g., 200:1) or no weights at all (1:1) in the two loss functions we considered: binary cross-entropy and a “soft” intersection-over-union (IOU) loss, a differentiable analogue to the IOU metric. The weighted cross-entropy loss, \mathcal{L}_{BCE} , is defined as in PyTorch’s BCEWithLogitsLoss function, and our IOU loss (inspired by [2,5]) is defined

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{IOU}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathbf{X}} w_{\text{frac}} \cdot y_i \cdot p_i}{\sum_{i \in \mathbf{X}} y_i + \sum_{i \in \mathbf{X}} p_i}.$$

where i is a voxel, $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is an indicator as to whether voxel i is a fracture, $p_i \in [0, 1]$ is the predicted probability that voxel i is a fracture, and w_{frac} is the fixed weight applied to fracture voxels.

Model Architecture and Training Details: We used a PyTorch implementation [6] based on a residual 3D U-Net [4] originally applied to neural circuit reconstruction from electron microscopic brain images. The architecture is like a standard 3D U-Net [1] except that (1) all skip connections use element-wise addition instead of concatenation and (2) each convolution block, or module, contains its own residual skip connection. Our base model had four convolution blocks, with 16 kernels applied at the first block, 32 at the second, and so on.¹

Most models were trained on four NVIDIA V100 GPUs and the training procedure was very standard (we used little to no “tricks” such as augmentation, learning rate scheduling, *etc.*). We used the Adam optimizer with a fixed learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and a batch size of 2, though when training larger models that occupied more GPU memory, we were forced to reduce the batch size to 1. Lastly, we trained our models for at least 75 epochs and restored model weights from the epoch with maximum validation IOU for final evaluation and submission. While submissions were not directly evaluated by IOU, we validated by IOU since (1) it is easy to compute and (2) it signals proper pixel-level segmentation, which would in turn aid proper fracture-level detection.

¹ This model had 2.2 million learnable parameters. Larger variants were created by increasing the number of blocks and number of kernels applied at each block.

Post-Processing Steps: After generating a predicted segmentation containing probabilities of fracture for each voxel, we first upsampled that prediction to the dimensions of the original input CT. We then thresholded that output to “binarize” our prediction and filled in, or closed, missing voxels in connected fracture regions with a morphological binary closing function. Next, we removed all small instances (less than 512 mm^3) to avoid over-predicting the number of fracture instances in a CT. Finally, since we modeled this task a semantic segmentation problem – ignoring instance information during training – we assigned instance labels by simply identifying and numbering the connected components in our final binary prediction. Lastly, we conducted a grid search to determine the set of post-processing hyperparameters (probability threshold, minimum fracture size, structuring elements used in morphological operations) that maximized the validation FROC for a given model. We then used these hyperparameters in all future runs. At the very end, we considered an ensemble of our two best models (by leaderboard detection FROC), simply averaging the voxel-wise probabilities predicted by these two models – one trained on \mathcal{L}_{BCE} and one on \mathcal{L}_{IOU} .

3 Results

Table 1 presents maximum validation IOU for various trained models by loss function used, fracture class weight w_{frac} , and number of learnable parameters. Note that these results do not reflect those of our final submissions since we did not apply the full post-processing pipeline to predictions before calculating IOU.² Overall, we see that models trained on \mathcal{L}_{IOU} were generally more successful than those trained on the more traditional \mathcal{L}_{BCE} . However, we find larger models – with more convolutional blocks and more kernels applied at each block – trained on \mathcal{L}_{BCE} outperformed smaller models. Finally, we see that, counter-intuitively, models with no class weights ($w_{\text{frac}} = 1$) outperformed otherwise identical models that placed 200-fold emphasis on fracture voxels in the loss ($w_{\text{frac}} = 200$).

Despite not having the highest validation IOUs, the models represented by rows two and four of Table 1 – after post-processing – achieved the highest detection FROC scores on the online test set (0.6109 and 0.6106, respectively). Seeing this, and given the proven capabilities of ensembling [3], we then generated predictions by taking the voxel-wise mean of fracture probabilities produced by these two models before applying our post-processing procedure. Hypothesizing

Loss	w_{frac}	Params	IOU
\mathcal{L}_{IOU}	1	2.2M	0.380
\mathcal{L}_{IOU}	200	2.2M	0.362
$\mathcal{L}_{IOU} + \mathcal{L}_{BCE}$	1	2.2M	0.331
\mathcal{L}_{BCE}	1	35.3M	0.321
\mathcal{L}_{BCE}	1	8.8M	0.303
\mathcal{L}_{BCE}	200	2.2M	0.234
\mathcal{L}_{BCE}	1	2.2M	0.292

Table 1: Summary of validation set ($n = 80$) results for various trained models. Validation IOU was calculated each epoch after applying a threshold of 0.5 to predictions.

² We only applied a threshold of 0.5 (which we later found to be suboptimal) before validating our model in order to save time during training.

that models trained on different objectives would benefit from combination, this ensemble model achieved our highest leaderboard detection FROC of 0.6665.

4 Discussion

It is interesting that our ensemble produced results dramatically better than any single model. Perhaps this is due to the fact that the two models that were averaged were trained on different losses. It may be justifiable that models trained on entirely different objectives would converge to different endpoints in their respective loss spaces, thus increasing the value of averaging their predictions.

Before training on whole, downsampled CTs, we attempted a patch-based approach, where we extracted full spatial resolution sub-volumes from each raw CT volume. While this seemed reasonable and promising, we found it took prohibitively long to train (on tens of thousands of patches) and was performing worse in terms of IOU than a whole-CT approach. It could be interesting to return to a patch-based approach as a means of refining the coarse predictions made by our whole-CT model.

Finally, we were able to achieve some success in this multi-instance detection task by essentially modeling the problem as a binary semantic segmentation task, ignoring both instance labels and fracture class (type) entirely. A model that can take advantage of instance information may outperform our current semantic segmentation approach. Additionally, knowledge about the class (type) of fracture may improve the quality of segmentation and detection via a multi-task loss.

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Detection Track CCCCS (DT6) & Classification Track CCCCS (CT4)

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Abstract. ResNet has been proved as one of the most successful classification backbones for image classification in recent years. We attempt to apply 3D ResNet18 to the MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge. To solve the problem of imbalance in dataset categories, the weighted cross-entropy loss has been used. Our classification method is based on the result of rib fracture semantic segmentation.

1 Introduction

Rib Fractures are the most frequently observed injury following thoracic trauma. Diagnosis of rib fractures serves as an important and common task in clinical practice, forensics, and several business scenarios [1]. However, the classification of rib fracture in the ribs on hundreds of slice CT images is a time-consuming and labor-intensive task. Misses diagnosis or misses classification caused by human is usually inevitable. Especially, some microscopic fractures such as buckle rib fracture, non-displaced rib fracture are at high risk of being miss diagnosis in artificial. An automatic and precise detection method is expected from rib fracture detection in the clinic.

However, no public dataset with multiple kinds of rib fractures has been available until now. This also leads to a relatively small number of semantic segmentation algorithms and classification algorithms that are specifically designed to detect rib fractures [2]. The rib fracture Detection and classification challenge (RibFrac 2020) [3] aims at solving this problem by providing 420 high quality annotated CT scans for training, 80 CT scans for validation, and 160 CT scans for algorithm testing.

Although this is a task independent of Task 1 in the RibFrac challenge 2020, considering the small size of the fracture area, we intend to realize rib fracture classification by classify the patch of the local area on the basis of Task1.

2 Method

2.1 Preprocessing and Dataset modifications

In fact, our preprocessing strategy for task 2 is based on the detection results of task 1. In our method only detected segmented regions will be classified.

Just like what we did in task one, each CT case is clipped to the range [-215, 585] and stretch the result to [0, 256]. Since the diameter of the labeled areas are concentrated between 10 and 60 pixels. We cut out the patch which size is 64*64*32 (W, H, D) voxels near the center of the marked area and upsample them to 128*128*64 pixels as the image for training and validating, and assign the corresponding annotations to these image blocks according to the challenging .csv file.

As mentioned before, 3988 patches were extracted from the training set and 436 patches were extracted from validation set. The training set included 179 cases of segmental rib fractures, 569 cases of non-displaced rib fractures, 618 cases of displaced rib fractures, 291 cases of buckle rib fractures and 2332 cases of neglected labeling in the test set, including 30 cases of segmental rib fractures, 63 cases of non-displaced rib fractures, 69 cases of displaced rib fractures, 30 cases of buckle rib fractures and 435 cases of neglected labeling.

2.2 Network architecture

For the backbone of the classification network, we have not made too many attempts. In fact, we only use the 3D variant version of the ResNet18 [4] as show in Fig. 1, which is currently the most mature method in image classification.

2.3 Loss Function

As stated previously, there is an extreme imbalance between the different classes in the data of this challenge. In addition, the long and narrow structure of the labeled rib fracture regions in the 3D region also brings some trouble for the extraction of patch. Therefore, when using the cross-entropy loss which is commonly used in classification tasks, we multiply the loss of each category by a certain weight. The weight of each category is the normalized results of the reciprocal of the sample number of each category in the training set.

2.4 Network training

We adopt Adam [5] as the optimizer and a batch size of 64 to train the network. The initial learning rate is 1e-4 and dropped by 0.5 on 4, 8, 16 epochs. The training of the network is carried out on four GPUs, utilizes 4.6 GB of VRAM on each GPU, and runs for about 12 hours. The training was done on Nvidia GeForce RTX 2080 GPUs (8G). Our network was implemented with the PyTorch framework [6] (version 1.1).

3 Result

The evaluation of the classification is based on the Macro-average F1 of the classification predictions and groundtruth labels.

Fig. 1. The 3D Res-Net18 architecture used in this project.

Since the fractures labeled 'ignore' are also classified as a category during training. Because the area marked as ignore accounts for a high proportion of the annotations given in the training set, there are a large number of samples misclassified as 'ignore' in the actual test, which leads to our best result F-score is only 0.22.

4 Discussion

Accurate and rapid diagnosis of different types of rib fractures can not only reduce the missed diagnosis rate and medical disputes, and improve the clinical prognosis of patients. At the same time, the accurate judgment of fracture occurrence and healing period will help clinical further guide treatment according to the degree of fracture healing, especially whether the fracture is bone healed. Will prompt the patient whether he can carry out daily weight-bearing work.

However, we don't know whether there is a problem with the data distribution of the corresponding data set for the current classification task, or whether our selection method cannot effectively classify the fracture image. The current experimental results still have a lot of room for improvement, which also prompts us to continue to find ways to improve classification accuracy in future study.

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Classification Track DeepBlueAI (CT3)

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Abstract. There are two tracks in MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge, rib fracture detection and classification. This report is the solution of DeepBlueAI for the classification task, which ranked 3rd place in the classification track. We analysis the challenge data set first. With the feature of the challenge data into consideration, we employ a dual pathway structure named DeepMedic[1] as our baseline. And adjust the structure of the baseline network, to make it more suitable for extracting the feature of the rib CT images. We optimize the model to reduce the false positive to obtain better classification results. The evaluation of the classification track is based on Macro-average F1 of the classification prediction and ground truth labels. Macro-average F1 score is the average of F1 score of each category. Final we get the results of 0.2332 on the test set.

Keywords: Rib fracture classification · CT images classification · 3D classification.

1 Introduction

Rib fracture detection and classification is an important application of computer vision assisted medical treatment. In MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge, there are five types of rib fracture: buckle rib fracture, non-displaced rib fracture, displaced rib fracture, segmental rib fracture and ambiguous fracture. Buckle rib fracture is a common entity in pediatric patients; There is a evident cortical disruption and a substantial abnormality in alignment in the case of displaced rib fracture, while not in non-displaced rib fracture; Segmental fractures are high-grade injuries with at least two separate complete fractures located in the same rib; For those that are ambiguous and difficult to determine the type of fracture, we call it ambiguous fracture, and ignore this type in classification task.

We analyzed the distribution of different types of fracture. In this competition, there are 420 CT images in training set, and 80 CT images in validation set. The distribution of different types of fractures is shown in Table 1. We find that there is a class imbalance in the challenge data.

The evaluation the classification is based on the Macro-average F1 of the classification predictions and ground truth labels. Macro-average F1 score is calculated by the average value of F1 scores of each categories. F1 score is calculated by

Table 1. Table 1. The distribution of different types of fracture.

Fracture type	Num in training set	Num in validation set	Total
displaced	618	69	687
non-displaced	567	63	630
buckle	291	30	321
segmental	179	30	209
ambiguous	2332	243	2575

equation (1). The Macro-average F1 score is calculated by equation (2), where t is the number of categories.

$$F1 = 2 * (Precision * Recall) / (Precision + Recall) \quad (1)$$

$$Macro - average F1 = (\sum_{i=1}^t (F1_i)) / t \quad (2)$$

2 Method

In this section, we will introduce the method we use in the classification task. We adopt DeepMedic as our baseline. The open source code we use is [2]. The overall structure of this neural network as shown in Figure 1. This method consists of two main components, a 3D CNN is used to produce highly accurate, soft segmentation features. And final segmentation labels are produced by a fully connected 3D CRF.

The 3D CNN employs a dual pathway architecture. The parallel convolution pathways efficiently incorporate both local and contextual information which greatly improves the segmentation performance, as the input resolution of parallel convolution pathway is different. There are shortcut connections in 4th, 6th and 8th CNN layer, which is similar with the shortcut structure of ResNet [3]. Shortcut connections, acting as cost-free element-wise addition, improve the efficiency of training and boost the performance of deep neural network.

In Figure 1, the layers of L_{N_i} and L_{L_i} are convolution layers, where $i = 0, \dots, 8$.

Fig. 1. The DeepMedic framework.

The upper branch is the normal resolution input branch, while the lower branch is the lower resolution branch. The kernel size of all of the convolution layers in Figure 1 is $3 * 3 * 3$ and the number of channel from L_{N1} to L_{N8} are [30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100] correspondingly. The structure of the bottom input branch is same as the normal input branch. L_9 and L_{10} are fully connected layers. The wide of the fully connected layer is 150. The 3D fully connected conditional random fields smooth the segmentation edges by spatial regularization.

3 Experiments

Baseline. We use the initial parameters of DeepMedic to train a baseline. With the initial learning rate is 0.001. The learning rate decreased by 2 at epoch [17, 22, 27, 30, 33] correspondingly. And the total epoch is 35. We use a momentum of 0.6, and use stochastic gradient descent to optimise the network. The input size is $37 * 37 * 37$ in training phrase while [45, 45, 45] for validation. The classification result on validation set is 0.1102.

Adjust Learning Schedule. The loss of baseline does not converge completely before the learning rate decrease, so we adjust the learning schedule. Inspired by the previous experience, with a lager initial learning rate can achieve better results when training from scratch. In order to ensure the network convergence completely, we user more iterations.

With the initial learning rate as 0.002 and total epoch as 70, we get the Macro-average F1 score 0.1546 on validation set.

```

Detection metrics
=====
Recall at key FP
      FP=0.5  FP=1  FP=2  FP=4  FP=8
Recall    0.0  0.0  0.0  0.0  0.528736
Average recall: 0.1057

Classification metrics
=====
Confusion matrix
      Buckle  Displaced  Nondisplaced  Segmental  FP  Ignore
Buckle    3.0    2.0    1.0    0.0  23.0   4.0
Displaced  4.0   22.0    9.0    3.0  43.0  15.0
Nondisplaced  2.0    7.0   14.0    4.0  18.0   8.0
Segmental  0.0    1.0    2.0    1.0   6.0   6.0
FN        13.0   12.0    8.0   12.0  0.0  140.0
Macro-average F1: 0.2227

```

Fig. 2. The performance on the validation set with larger input size

Larger Test Patch. We test different input size, such as $64 * 64 * 64$, $72 * 72 * 72$, $96 * 96 * 96$, on the validation dataset. We find that with the input size $72 * 72 * 72$ can obtain better results on validation set. The classification result increases from 0.1546 to 0.2227. The result is shown in Figure 2.

```

Detection metrics
=====
Recall at key FP
      FP=0.5  FP=1  FP=2   FP=4   FP=8
Recall    0.0  0.0  0.0  0.43908  0.43908
Average recall: 0.1756

Classification metrics
=====
Confusion matrix
      Buckle  Displaced  Nondisplaced  Segmental  FP  Ignore
Buckle      3.0      1.0      1.0      0.0  17.0   2.0
Displaced   4.0     20.0      7.0      3.0  30.0  12.0
Nondisplaced 0.0      6.0     14.0      4.0  10.0   6.0
Segmental   0.0      1.0      1.0      1.0   3.0   5.0
FN          16.0     16.0     14.0     13.0  0.0  168.0
Macro-average F1: 0.2430

```

Fig. 3. The result on the validation dataset after removing small parts

Other Attempts. From Figure 2, we can see that False Positive predictions result in poor results. We remove the very small connected domains in predictions, where the number of voxels is smaller than 30. The classification results increase from 0.2104 to 0.2430. On the validation data set and get a performance of 0.2332 on test data set. The result is shown in Figure 3.

Apart from the aforementioned experiments before, we also make other attempts, such as changing the weights of loss, data augmentation and so on, but do not work for improving the performance. And we have tried other network, such as 3D UNet[4], VNet[5]. But the performance of these networks are not satisfactory.

4 Conclusion

We train the rib fracture CT images with DeepMedic network, with larger initial learning rate, more iterations, larger input get the Macro-average F1 score 0.2332 which ranks 3rd place in MICCAI 2020 RibFrac Challenge classification task. We hope our work will attract more attention to the application of computer vision in medical field.

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